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Project management plan and quality guidelines Version 1.0

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Executive Summary

The purpose of the *Management plan and quality guidelines* is to provide an overview of the internal management procedures for the eProcessor project, and to ensure both efficient project execution and high-quality project results. It also serves as a support reference manual for project partners as it describes, in a comprehensible way, the governance structure, the reference project legal documents, the project management procedures and tools, and the reporting procedure. It also includes roles and responsibilities and the internal monitoring process for project progress.

Planning the management procedures contributes to the management objectives of the project and indirectly influences its technical implementation by ensuring an efficient working environment.

1. Project Coordination and Management

eProcessor is a consortium of 10 partners from 6 EU member states. This section describes the organization of the consortium's governance bodies, planned project meetings, and interactions toward effective project implementation.

1.1 Governance structure

The project organizational structure includes the following key components: 1) Project Coordinator (Technical Manager and Project Manager), General Assembly, Technical Board and Work Package Leaders, Innovation Manager, and Scientific Advisory Board. The interactions between these different components and their responsibilities are described in the sections below.

1.1.1 Project Coordination

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC, Beneficiary no.1), is the Coordinating organization of the eProcessor project. The *Project Coordinator (PC)*, Nehir Sonmez, who is also the *Technical Manager (TM)*, has the overall responsibility for the project progress and guarantees that the scientific and technical objectives of the project are met.

The PC/TM chairs the *General Assembly (GA)* comprising of one delegate from each beneficiary, and leads the *Technical Board (TB)* formed by *Work Package Leaders (WPL)* and one representative per partner organization. The TM defines the high-level technical strategy to be followed to achieve the project goals and ensures that the project maintains its relevance to the H2020-JTI-EuroHPC-2019-1 and its strategic objectives. Furthermore, the TM chairs the *Technical Board (TB)*, organizes technical presentations of project progress to external parties and ensures the appropriate involvement and visibility of the project members. The TM also works with WPLs to identify and track possible problems and propose suitable corrective actions. The TM is also responsible for calling TB meetings as well as compiling and distributing minutes and action plans.

The *Project Manager (PM)*, Julianna Anguelova (BSC), is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the project and ensures the timely delivery of project objectives and deliverables by continuously monitoring how closely the project progress is following the plan set in the Grant Agreement. Activities within the day-to-day management include: organizing meetings,

following deliverable progress and timely submission, monitoring quality control, and risk management. The administrative and financial management of the project is also the responsibility of the PM. This includes monitoring the internal use of resources, preparing and submitting Periodic Reports and Financial Statements. In addition, the PM ensures timely and efficient distribution of EU funding according to the Grant Agreement.

The PC and PM are responsible for all the project administrative matters and act as the official link between the eProcessor Consortium and the European Commission (EC).

1.1.2 General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA), chaired by the PC, is the decision-making body of the project and is formed by one delegate from each beneficiary. Each partner has one vote, with the vote of the chairperson deciding in case of a tie. The GA provides a forum for the discussion of administrative and strategic management issues linked to the project. In addition, it decides on approving major modifications to project plans, allocated efforts, and budget issues. The GA assembles every 6 months during face-to-face or online meetings.

Table 1 presents the members of the eProcessor General Assembly.

No.	Beneficiary short name	Representative
1	BSC	Nehir Sonmez (Chairperson)
2	Chalmers	Ioannis Sourdis
3	Forth	Vassilis Papaefstathiou
4	UNIRM	Mauro Olivieri
5	Cortus	Christophe Genevois
6	CHR	Stefan Krupop
7	UNIBI	Jens Hagemeyer
8	Extoll	Mondrian Nuessle
9	Thales	Nicolas Ventroux
10	Exapsys	Iakovos Mavroidis

Table 1. eProcessor General Assembly

1.1.3 Technical Board

The TB is composed of the Technical Manager, the Project Manager, the Work Package Leaders, along with a member of each beneficiary organization. It takes part in resource allocation decisions, reviews and approves Deliverables and Periodic Reports, the preparation of project reviews, and the coordination of exploitation plans. The TB holds monthly teleconference calls in order to exchange information, coordinate and review project progress, and assess risks in a timely manner. It makes decisions on implementation issues by consensus. In case the TB cannot obtain consensus with respect to an issue, the issue is forwarded to the GA and, if needed, subjected to a vote.

Table 2 presents the members of the eProcessor TB:

WP No.	Beneficiary short name	Work package leader
TM (Chair)	BSC	Nehir Sonmez
1	BSC	Julianna Anguelova
2	Exapsys	Yannis Papaefstathiou
3	BSC	Lluc Alvarez
4	Chalmers	Miquel Pericas / Mustafa Abduljabbar
5	BSC	Nehir Sonmez
6	FORTH	Vassilis Papaefstathiou
7	Cortus	Christophe Genevois
	Beneficiary short name	Partner representative
	UNIRM	Mauro Olivieri
	UNIBI	Jens Hagemeyer
	Extoll	Niels Burkhardt
	Chalmers	Ioannis Sourdis
	Thales	Nicolas Ventroux
	Christmann	Stefan Krupop
	Cortus	Michael Chapman
	Exapsys	Iakovos Mavroidis

Table 2. eProcessor Technical Board

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs) are responsible for the scientific and technical work of their respective WPs. This includes planning and control of all activities and the collection of contributions from partners participating in the WP. The WP internal technical discussions and work will be led by WPLs, while inter-WP issues will be addressed by the TB.

1.1.4 Innovation Manager

The Innovation Manager (IM) is Yannis Papaefstathiou (EXAPSYS), who also leads the Dissemination and Exploitation work package, and coordinates partners' efforts dedicated to innovation management. In particular, the IM ensures that appropriate communication mechanisms are in place to raise awareness internally regarding the project's innovation processes. The IM's role is also to supervise the creation, sharing, update, storage, and protection of documented information, providing evidence regarding the effectiveness of the innovation management approach. Additionally, the IM is in charge of defining guidelines for the management of intangible assets developed by the project (including knowledge and know-how) and the IP. He also manages collaboration with external stakeholders and EU projects, competitive intelligence, and identification of commercialization, standardization, and exploitation opportunities.

1.1.5 Scientific Advisory Board

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) provides an efficient, independent mechanism for quickly obtaining real-world academic and industrial feedback on project interim results. Moreover, it facilitates broader academic and industrial direct participation in identifying and pursuing exploitation opportunities. The SAB is tasked with providing input to the team on an annual basis. This feedback is provided via Technical SAB Meetings. The full SAB is not yet complete and will be complemented by additional members with expertise areas that reflect the activity state-space of this project.

Table 3 presents the current members of the eProcessor SAB:

No.	SAB Member	Host Organization
1	Luca Benini (academic)	ETH Zurich (EPI STX accelerator lead)
2	Thomas Lippert (academic)	Jülich Supercomputing Centre (Head)
3	Jesus Labarta (academic)	BSC (POP2 CoE Coordinator)
4	Elio Guidetti (industrial)	STMicro

Table 3. eProcessor Scientific Advisory Board

1.2 Project Meetings

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the associated travel and gathering restrictions, the meetings and events planned in the framework of the eProcessor project have been adapted to the current scenario. Therefore, for the first year of the project, all project meetings are held online. In the future, the format of meetings and events will be reassessed depending on the evolution of the present pandemic.

Kick-off Meeting. The eProcessor Kick-off Meeting took place on April 19, 2021 as a teleconference (via Zoom). Although some technical meetings were held before, the meeting marked the official start of the project's technical implementation, set the work plan for the following 6 months, and helped finalize the administrative details described in the current Project management plan.

GA Meetings. In the original project work plan, the GA meetings were foreseen as face-to-face meetings held every 6 months. Under the current circumstances dictated by the COVID-19 pandemic, in the first year of the project, GA meetings will be held online (via Zoom). The PC and PM prepare the meeting agenda, chair the meeting, and provide the meeting minutes at the end of the event.

If possible (in the second year of the project), future face-to-face GA meetings are hosted by each partner on a rotational basis, whereby the host is responsible for organizing the meeting rooms and IT equipment, while the PC and PM prepare the meeting agenda, chair the meeting, and provide the minutes of the meeting at the end of the event.

General status meetings and TB meetings: Bi-weekly teleconferences are scheduled on Tuesdays to review the general status and overall progress of the project on a regular basis. On the last Tuesday of the month, the TB meets after the general status meeting to discuss progress, assess risks and action points to be implemented. Zoom software is used to facilitate online information sharing. The TM and PM collect slides in advance, chair the meeting and provide collaborative meeting notes via a shared drive. These are then sent through the project mailing list and stored on the internal project repository.

WP Meetings. Each WPL organizes weekly or biweekly online meetings to monitor and coordinate the activities inside their respective WP. Moreover, bilateral WP meetings are organized whenever necessary to address the dependencies between the various WPs (Figure 1).

The WPLs prepare the meeting agendas, chair the meetings, and provide the meeting minutes at the end of the event via the project repository.

Figure 1. This diagram provides a linear view, from left to right, of the eProcessor cyclic co-design workflow. Note that there can be multiple iterations of the implementation and feedback, and revision phases.

1.3 Conflict of interest

Goodwill to avoid any conflict of interest and to act in good faith is essential for the success of the eProcessor project. When Beneficiaries identify conflicts of interest that cannot be resolved through bilateral communication, they should bring the issues to the PC's attention immediately. The PC presents the issue to the General Assembly for discussion and hold a vote if required.

1.4 Emergency Procedure

Any event that may jeopardize the overall completion of the project should be reported immediately to the PC. The PC endeavours to resolve the issue as soon as possible by calling an emergency General Assembly Meeting in order to determine the next steps.

2. Legal documents

2.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is the main legal document underpinning the project's execution. It is a contract between the project participants and the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC). The Grant Agreement mainly provides information on the grant (parties, duration, start date, budget, maximum funding, etc.), obligations of the beneficiaries towards the funding agency (such as reporting requirements), as well as the intellectual

property framework and other legal conditions. The eProcessor Grant Agreement is dated on April 1, 2021 and has number 956702.

Beyond its core terms and conditions, mostly standard text, the Grant Agreement also includes the following annexes, which form an integral part of the contract:

- Annex I. Description of the action (DoA)
- Annex II. Estimated budget for the action
- Annex III. Accession form for beneficiaries
- Annex IV. Financial statement
- Annex V. Model for the certificate on financial statements
- Annex VI. Model for the certificate on the methodology

The most extensive and important Annex to the Grant Agreement is the Description of Action (DoA), which comprises the technical description of the work to be undertaken in the project (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones), the roles of the different partners, allocated efforts in person-months, and budget details.

2.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) is a document concluded between the project participants and aims to provide a legal framework for their collaboration within the boundaries of the Grant Agreement. The CA includes provisions on governance, intellectual property, dissemination, and liability, among others. EuroHPC is not a party to the CA.

2.3 Changes to the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed when an important project parameter changes: partnership, duration, budget, etc. Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called “Grant Agreement Amendment”. Most changes that trigger Grant Agreement amendments relate to updates in the DoA (e.g., changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, changes in partner’s teams, budget transfers across participants, etc.). Whenever it is possible, changes tend to be grouped and implemented all at once in an amendment.

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the European Commission through the Funding and Tenders portal by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be informed and agree on the proposed changes before the amendment is requested. The PM is responsible for preparing and follow-up the amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project. Participants should contact the PM and TM for any modification they consider necessary. The PM should contact the Project Officer to inform them about the proposed changes before launching the amendment officially through the portal.

3. Internal communication

To ensure proper project implementation, internal communication is essential. The eProcessor Consortium uses electronic mail as the main tool of communication and document all meetings by means of agenda and minutes, which are made available through the official project repository (B2DROP).

3.1 Mailing lists

The following mailing lists have been created to facilitate the internal communication:

- eprocessor-general@bsc.es: all eProcessor contacts;
- eprocessor-leads@bsc.es: Work package leaders list;
- eprocessor-tb@bsc.es: eProcessor TB members;
- eprocessor-info@bsc.es: general mailing list linked to project website;
- eprocessor-wp1@bsc.es: WP1 participants;
- eprocessor-wp2@bsc.es: WP2 participants;
- eprocessor-wp3@bsc.es: WP3 participants;
- eprocessor-wp4@bsc.es: WP4 participants;
- eprocessor-wp5@bsc.es: WP5 participants;
- eprocessor-wp6@bsc.es: WP6 participants;
- eprocessor-wp7@bsc.es: WP7 participants;

The mailing lists are administered by the PM, who is responsible for granting access to any new eProcessor team member.

3.2 Zoom Video Communications

Zoom Video Communications services are used for remote conferencing for general status bi-weekly meetings, General Assembly meetings, and technical meetings as needed.

3.3 B2DROP repository

A B2DROP project repository based on Nextcloud (hosted by BSC) has been created as an intranet in order to keep track of project results, official project documents, and other relevant files useful for project implementation (i.e., Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, Templates, Meetings including minutes, etc.). An overview of the B2DROP repository structure is illustrated below.

Figure 2. B2DROP project repository structure

3.4 Gitlab

A Gitlab repository (hosted by BSC) has been created to facilitate the exchange of technical documentation during the project's implementation. The repository includes functionalities such as wiki, issue-tracking, and CI/CD pipeline that can be used throughout the project. The TM grants access to the Gitlab repository.

4. Project management procedures and tools

4.1 Financial management

In order to continuously monitor the financial status of the project, the partners are required to provide information on project expenses every six months. For this, the PM provides an internal financial report template, where they indicate the person months incurred across the WPs they are involved in, and other costs together with their justification. This exercise allows

the project coordination team to detect any potential deviations and take corrective actions when necessary.

eProcessor Internal Financial Reporting			
Please fill in the fields marked with yellow concerning the estimated Personnel Effort and Major Cost items for the Period and send to julianna.angelova@bsc.es			
Beneficiary:			
Period:	M1-M6		01/04/2021 - 31/10/2021
PERSONNEL COSTS			
WP title	ACTUAL Person Month (PM)	Personnel costs (EUR)	
WP1 - Coordination and Management			
WP2- Dissemination and Exploitation			
WP3 - Software Applications Use Cases, Specifications and Evaluation			
WP4 - Tools, OS and System Software			
WP5 - Architecture, RTL Design and Verification			
WP6 - System Simulation and FPGA Emu			
WP7 - Chip Fabrication, PCB development and Validation			
Total	0,00		0,00 €
OTHER DIRECT COSTS (ODC)			
Category	WP	Description (Please indicate dates, name of meeting, names of attendees or other goods and services)	Cost (EUR)
Total			0
TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (Personnel + ODC)			0,00 €
INDIRECT COSTS (25% of total direct costs)			0,00 €
TOTAL COSTS			0,00 €

Figure 3: eProcessor internal financial report template

4.2 Deliverable quality criteria and review procedure

Project deliverables are the outcome of the technical progress across the various WPs during the project's implementation. As a general rule, the generation of deliverables is the responsibility of the corresponding WPLs, who need to gather contributions from WP participants as appropriate. Prior to submission to the Funding and Tenders Portal, deliverables are examined against a set of quality criteria and undergo an internal review process, as detailed in subsections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2, respectively. For the eProcessor project, the types of deliverables included are reports, demonstrators and those in other formats.

The eProcessor deliverable template, including a general deliverable structure, was shared with all partners and is also available on the B2DROP repository.

4.2.1 Quality criteria

The review procedure uses the following quality criteria as reference:

- **Completeness.** Information must address all aspects related to the purpose for which the information is produced. Redundancy of information must be avoided, as it may obscure the clarity of the deliverables. Information should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.
- **Accuracy.** Information provided in the deliverable must be evidence-based. This means that all factual information used in the deliverables should be supported by relevant and up-to-date references.

- **Relevance.** Information used in the deliverable should be focused on the key issues and be written in a way that takes into consideration its target audience.
- **Adherence to uniform appearance.** It is important that deliverables are prepared with a uniform appearance and structure so that they appear to originate from a single initiative. Therefore, the eProcessor deliverable template (provided by the Dissemination Manager) is to be used for all deliverables.

4.2.2 Review procedure

The Deliverable Review Procedure is meant to ensure that the document has been reviewed against the set of quality criteria described above. The 31 deliverables of the eProcessor project have been distributed among 10 partners such that each partner is responsible for reviewing between 3-4 deliverables to ensure a fair workload distribution. This does not exclude other partners not appointed as reviewers to provide their comments on the different deliverables if they wish to do so. The list of deliverables and their corresponding appointed reviewers are available on B2DROP.

The following table summarizes the internal deliverable review process established to ensure the timely submission of deliverables.

Timeframe	Review action
5 weeks before the deadline	The PM sends a reminder to the author of the upcoming deliverable/s; the PM informs about the appointed reviewer indicating when the draft should be ready to send for review.
3 weeks before the deadline	The author sends the draft deliverable to the appointed reviewer for comments.
2 weeks before the deadline	The appointed reviewer sends his/her comments back to the author (Track changes document).
5 days before the deadline	The author sends the consolidated deliverable back to the reviewer.
2 days before the deadline	The reviewer confirms that the deliverable is accepted, and the author sends the final version to the PM.
Submission deadline	The PM reviews the format and deliverable label before uploading the document to the Funding and Tenders portal.

Table 4. eProcessor Deliverable Review Procedure

When rejecting a deliverable, the reviewer must provide to the deliverable author, in writing, constructive suggestions for improvement. Upon receiving the suggestions for improvement, the deliverable author must determine together with the Project Manager the updated schedule to complete the deliverable.

4.3 Milestone management

At the end of each key phase in the project, a milestone is set up to perform technical reviews and make strategic decisions to guarantee that the progress of the project is in line with the project objectives. Five main milestones map to significant achievements across all layers of the eProcessor stack. Table 5 and Figure 2 present the eProcessor milestones, while the means of verification for each of them can be found in the DoA.

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related WPs	Milestone date
MS1	Specifications: Project Management and Quality Guidelines, system specifications, and requirements.	WP1, WP3	M3
MS2	Single-core RTL: Dissemination and exploitation plan, Microbenchmarks, Accelerator, and Out-of-order core RTL freeze, Simulation and FPGA infrastructures.	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	M12
MS3	Single-core Tapeout: Dissemination and exploitation reports, Use-case applications, Single-core hardware and software (OS and tools for FPGA emulation, chip RTL freeze, and verification, FPGA emulation, Tapeout, PCB, first firmware and BSP release).	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	M18
MS4	Multi-core RTL: OS and tools for single-core, Multi-core chip RTL freeze and verification.	WP4, WP5	M27
MS5	Multi-core Tapeout: Final dissemination and exploitation reports, Performance analysis, optimizations, and evaluation of use-case applications, Multi-core hardware and software (OS and tools, FPGA emulation, Tape-out, PCB, final firmware and BSP release), eProcessor RTL release.	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	M36

Table 5: eProcessor Summary of Milestones

Figure 4: eProcessor milestones

The timeline in Figure 4 will shift accordingly in line with the later project start date in April 2021. The figure mainly illustrates the sequence of the project milestones.

4.4 Risk management

The eProcessor risk management process includes all activities to identify, assess, prioritize, manage, and control risks that may affect the execution of the project and the achievement of its objectives.

Because of the complex nature of the activities required for project execution, some risks could affect the full accomplishment of its objectives. These have been identified in advance, and mitigation measures have been arranged for each potential situation (as detailed in the eProcessor DoA and Table 6 of this document). However, unforeseen risks may arise as the project evolves and they should be monitored throughout the project lifecycle. Analysis of deliverable status, WP objectives and periodic reports analysis are considered as tools for risk identification. In addition, brainstorming meetings might be organized among work packages leaders in order to identify new potential risks.

Risks have been assessed based on their level of likelihood (Low, Medium or High). The PM, with support from the WPLs are responsible for evaluating risks throughout the project.

Description of risk	Related WPs	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
<p>R1 (LOW): Losing a critical partner at a crucial point in the project This risk belongs to the category of inevitable ones in any partnership - namely changes to the direction and/or business of one or more partners leading to their withdrawal from the project.</p>	All WPs	Risk effect is dependent on the partner, the work affected, and the timing. Relatively to the core partners already present in previous H2020 projects (BSC, FORTH, CHAL, etc.), the likelihood of this risk is extremely low, since these partners already have a close collaboration history, sharing a common vision and a strong and long-term commitment. In the quite unlikely case of a partner withdrawing, an adapted contingency plan would be quickly established and shared with the H2020 EU officers, permitting to pursue the global objectives and to limit the impacts on the scope of work.
<p>2 (LOW): Disagreement among partners Again the likelihood of this risk is low, since most of the partners have collaborated successfully in the past.</p>	All WPs	To reduce the risk, there should be strong leadership at the work package and project level. If disagreements arise, the project coordinator is responsible for solving conflict situations and proposing an adapted plan, helped by the project management structures.
<p>R3 (MEDIUM): Not meeting the progress of the competition The proposed research will result in a beyond state-of-the-art energy efficient HPC processor. Nevertheless, the competition can also make progress and at the end the eProcessor outcome could be outperformed.</p>	All WPs	The Project Technical Board will constantly monitor the competition evolution and if necessary provide more aggressive targets to the WPs. The co-design approach of the eProcessor project and the several innovation fields (energy efficiency, fault tolerance, accelerators, etc.) should enable the project to define differentiators from the competition.
<p>R4 (LOW): Not being able to port all target applications.</p>	WP3	The risk is very low thanks to the emulation platform, having a main role of software development vehicles. To

Some applications may require much larger than expected efforts for porting them to the RISC-V architecture.		minimize the impact of this risk, we will select applications amenable to porting to the target RISC-V platform.
R5 (LOW): Delayed delivery of OS and boot environment. The possibility for such a delay could arise due to lacking an adequate HW environment, e.g. not stable enough platform.	WP4	The risk is very low, thanks to the emulation platform having a main role of software development vehicles. Extra effort needs to be undertaken during the specification phase to ensure that an appropriate HW environment will be provided. To ensure that at least the most critical features are supported, we will define an early internal milestone to speed-up this work.
R6 (LOW): The system software is not delivered in time. The risk is low because most software components are either already available for RISC-V or just require a recompilation. However, some components may present higher than expected complexity.	WP4	The risk is very low, thanks to the emulation platform having a main role of software development vehicles. To minimize this risk, we will survey the status of all software components early on in the project and classify those that potentially pose higher risk. A higher effort will be allocated to deal with such components.
R7 (MEDIUM): Potentially some critical timing issues in the single-core chip may result in RTL changes to improve the critical path.	WP5, WP7	Perform rapidly a full chip synthesis to gain an understanding as to where the potential problems may lie and also to drive the floor plan. For paths which are simply too long, the path will be broken by pipelining wherever possible. Most of the RTL design will be done in such a way that a pipeline stage can be inserted in most places without changing functionality (but obviously with an impact on latency). The coherent interconnect, which is being used for interconnect between the different on-chip and off-chip caches will support the insertion of elastic buffers to pipeline long links.
R8 (LOW): Potentially some critical timing issues in the dual-core chip may result in RTL changes to improve the critical path.	WP5, WP7	Any issues should be able to be solved with a better floor plan and exceptionally with an additional pipeline stage in the NOC links, possibly using elastic buffers.
R9 (LOW): Delayed delivery of accelerator block - Delay in RTL core freeze of any accelerators.	WP5	In the case of a delay in any of the accelerators, we will reconfigure the related software stack to support this functionality with reduced performance in another accelerator, when possible.
R10 (LOW): MEEP emulation platform immature , but as a raw FPGA, it is still useful for the single core design emulator.	WP6	Multiple mitigation plans are available, leveraging the facilities available from different partners. As an example, the FORTH FPGA platform may be more mature and also a single FPGA add-on card can be used as the third alternative.
R11 (LOW): Integration at physical level presents bugs.	WP7	The risk of bugs arising at the physical integration stage of digital IPs is very low. This is ensured by using static timing analysis (to ensure there are no hold violations on any registers/memories) and

		equivalence checking (to ensure that the chip's physical design matches the RTL).
R12 (LOW): Delay in the tape out of the first chip due to misalignment between the MPW run schedule and the starting date of the project.	WP7	The delay would be limited to a couple of months and would result in compression of the time to design the second chip, leveraging the results of testing the first chip. The emulation platform will largely mitigate the need for re-design due to design bugs emerging in the bring-up and testing phase.

Table 6: eProcessor critical risks and mitigation strategies

5. Reporting and Reviews

5.1 Periodic reporting

During the eProcessor execution period (from April 1, 2021 to March 31, 2024), the Consortium must submit 2 periodic reports. In compliance with the Horizon 2020 rules specified in Article 20.3 of the eProcessor Grant Agreement, periodic reports must be submitted within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. For eProcessor these are at M18 and M36:

- First Reporting Period: April 1, 2021 – September 30, 2022 (M18);
- Second Reporting Period: October 1, 2022 – March 31, 2024 (M36).

Each periodic report consists of a technical and a financial report that must describe the technical activities and costs incurred over the corresponding period specified above.

5.1.1 Technical Report

The technical report consists of two parts:

1. *PART A* can be updated at any time during the lifetime of the project. This has to be done through the Funding and Tenders portal under the Continuous Reporting Module. It consists of the following sections:
 - Summary for publication,
 - Deliverables, Ethics, DMP, Other Reports,
 - Milestones,
 - Critical Risks,
 - Publications,
 - Dissemination & Communication Activities,
 - Patents (IPR),
 - Innovation,
 - Open Data,
 - Gender,
 - ABS Regulation.

The project Coordinator, supported by the PM and all the other partners, is responsible for collecting and entering the information in the appropriate sections for Continuous Reporting. Regarding the dissemination and exploitation of results, the WP2 leader, as Dissemination lead, keeps track of the project's dissemination activities for the purpose of periodic reporting. Participants are asked regularly to send updates on any dissemination activity related to eProcessor. The Dissemination lead integrates all the available information in a general dissemination tracking table.

2. PART B is the core part of the report and follows the template made available by the European Commission. Therefore, it has to be uploaded to the grant management tool as a single document, including:
 - Details of the work carried out by all beneficiaries during the reporting period, and
 - An overview of the progress towards the project objectives, justifying any differences between the work described in Annex I (DoA) and the work actually performed.

In close collaboration with the project partners, the Coordinator is responsible for elaborating Part B of the Periodic Technical Report and uploading the file to the portal within the specified timelines.

5.1.2 Financial Report

5.1.2.1. eProcessor eligible costs

For incurred project costs to be eligible and therefore approved by the Funding Agency, they must fulfill the following general conditions:

- They must be incurred by the beneficiary.
- Incurred during the duration of the project, with the exception of costs related to the submission of the periodic report for the last reporting period and the final report.
- Indicated in the estimated overall budget in Annex II.
- Actual and necessary for the project's implementation.
- They must be identifiable, verifiable, and recorded in the participants' accounts.
- Registered in accordance with the usual accounting practices of the participant.
- They must comply with the applicable national law on taxes and social security.
- They must be reasonable and justified, and must comply with the principle of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency.

5.1.2.2 Financial Statements for each beneficiary

The Financial Report is composed of Individual Financial Statements for each beneficiary, together with an explanation on the use of resources. Financial statements are specific documents in which each participant declares all the costs incurred over the corresponding reporting period.

The justification of costs is done through the Funding and Tenders Portal by using the Periodic Reporting Module (which is made available to the participants after the end of the corresponding reporting period by the Project Officer). Each beneficiary must fill in and detail their own expenses. Once the input information is complete, the beneficiary must electronically sign the Financial Statement. Only users with the role of Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) can perform this action. Once all Financial Statements have been signed by all beneficiaries (including the Coordinator), the Coordinator checks that all information is correct and includes the Financial Statements in the Periodic Report composition.

Specific guidelines for accessing the *Periodic Reporting Module* will be prepared by the PM. These guidelines include screenshots and instructions for adequate reporting and are to be made available to all participants as supporting material.

5.1.2.3. Explanation on the deviations from the planned budget

In addition to the financial statements for each beneficiary, an explanation of any deviation from the costs forecasted in Annexes I and II of the Grant Agreement should be provided in Part B of the Periodic technical report. Moreover, information on unforeseen subcontracting and unforeseen in-kind contributions provided by third parties (if any) should also be provided and properly justified. The PM is responsible for collecting and compiling the information from all beneficiaries. To that end, the PM monitors every 6 months the effort and costs incurred by all partners as described in section 4.1 of this document.

5.1.2.4. Periodic Report submission

The Coordinator is responsible for approving the Financial Statements of each beneficiary and revising all information included in the Technical Report (Part A and Part B). Once all information is complete, the Coordinator submits the Periodic Report to EuroHPC through the Funding and Tenders Portal.

5.2 Final Report

Within 60 days after the end of the project, and in addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the Consortium must also submit a final report to the Funding Agency.

The final report must include the following:

1. A 'Final technical report' with a summary for publication containing:
 - an overview of the project results and their exploitation and dissemination,
 - the conclusions on the action, and
 - the socio-economic impact of the action.
2. A 'Final financial report' containing:
 - a 'final summary financial statement', created automatically by the electronic system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods, and including the request for payment of the balance; and
 - a 'certificate on the financial statements' for each beneficiary who requests a total contribution of EUR 325,000 (excluding indirect costs) or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of their usual cost accounting practices.

This final report will be prepared by the TM and the PM, with input from the other WPLs who will compile all necessary inputs from all partners involved in each respective work package.

5.3 Reviews

The Funding Agency carries out checks and reviews on the proper implementation of the action (including assessment of deliverables and reports). Reviews usually refer mainly to the technical implementation of the project (i.e. its scientific and technological relevance), but may also cover financial and budgetary aspects or compliance with other obligations under the Grant Agreement. The eProcessor reviews are scheduled for Month 18 (September 2022) and Month 36 (March 2024) at the EuroHPC premises in Luxembourg. However, dates and location are tentative and are subject to changes based on the flexibility and availability of the Project Officer, of the selected reviewers, and of the project partners, and also on the health recommendations at the respective time (e.g., traveling and gathering restrictions due to COVID-19 pandemic).

6. Conclusion

This document outlined the internal management procedures, tools, monitoring and reporting procedures, governance structure, and roles and responsibilities specific to the eProcessor project.

To the extent that it is deemed necessary by the Consortium, the procedures will be reviewed to ensure that the management objectives are met and that the implementation of the project is carried out in an efficient manner.

7. Acronyms and Abbreviations

BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Chalmers	Chalmers University of Technology
CHR	Christmann
Cortus	Cortus SAS
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
eProcessor	European, extendable, energy-efficient, extreme-scale, extensible, Processor Ecosystem
Exapsys	EXAscale Performance SYStems p.c
Extoll	Extoll GmbH
Forth	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas
GA	General Assembly
IM	Innovation Manager
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
TB	Technical Board
Thales	Thales Research & Technology
TM	Technical Manager
UNIBI	University of Bielefeld
UNIRM	Sapienza University of Rome
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader